

HAPPINESS AND WELLBEING AT WORKPLACE: A REVIEW OF STUDIES IN LAST THIRTY YEARS

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Introduction

Since ancient times, happiness has been one of the most fundamental topics of debate and discussion. Several theories and definitions have been provided to provide a precise definition of happiness. The ancient Greek philosophers argued over the definition of happiness. Heraclitus, a hedonist, associated happiness with pleasure, enjoyment, and comfort, whereas Aristotle believed happiness to be Eudemon, the pursuit of meaningfulness (Jayawickreme et al., 2008), a journey toward holistic improvement. The Greek term eudemonia literally means "Wellbeing." The age-old philosophical debate between hedonism and eudaimonism continues, but there has been a tremendous emergence of new ideas regarding Well-Being and Happiness. Initially, it is essential to recognize that well-being and happiness, despite their apparent similarity in dimension and characteristics, are two distinct concepts that may be intertwined but do not share a complete affinity. According to Martin E. P. Seligman (Seligman, 2002), well-being is a construct, whereas happiness is a real thing that can be directly measured; therefore, happiness is a measurable entity. Happiness is consequently measured primarily in terms of Life Satisfaction, whereas Well-Being is a construct comprised of a number of contributing factors, which he elucidates with his PERMA model. Positive Emotion, Engagement, Relationships, Meaning, and Accomplishments are the contributing factors of PERMA (Seligman, 2011)

In a modern and simplistic statute, happiness is defined as something we choose for its own sake (Seligman, 2002), which can be measured and analysed based on three standard components:

- Positive emotion that encompasses what we experience, such as warmth, pleasure, comfort, ecstasy, etc. A life that is satisfying and associated with such emotions is unquestionably a "meaningful life."
- Engagement or Flow – Being absorbed or captivated by the present experience. When we are firmly rooted in the immediate experience of what we are doing. A life of Flow is defined as a life of engagement.
- Meaning – we can only claim to have lived a meaningfully satisfying life if we pursue activities for their own sake.

On the other hand, well-being as a concept has been undergoing rigorous revivals, and the emerging trends and parameters to understand it have consequently altered its dynamics. A model known as the MPWB (Multidimensional Psychological Well-Being) criterion has been developed in order to comprehend the complexities of happiness in the modern era. Where well-being is defined as the combination of feeling good and functioning well. A combination of telling content, having certain aspirations to demonstrate personal potential, having control over one's own life, and having a sense of life's purpose are detrimental to Well-being. Subjective Well-being has been found to be synonymous with positive mental health. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines mental health as "a state of well-being in which the individual realises his or her own abilities, can deal with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to one's community." It is necessary for us to define well-being in either a hedonistic or a eudemonistic light; however, this decision is risky; therefore, an informative measure of well-being must include both brackets and cannot be evaluated as a unitary variable. According to Huppert and So, positive mental health or Well-being can be viewed as the polar opposite of mental illness; consequently, an attempt was made to define it in terms that are the inverse of the symptoms of common mental disorders as listed in the DSM and ICD. 10 such symptoms were identified whose opposite elements were recognised as the criteria of Well- Being: Competence, emotional stability, engagement, meaning, optimism, positive emotion, positive relationships, resilience, self-Esteem, and vitality.

Need for workplace happiness and wellbeing

Employees' workplace happiness influence goal realization, feedback, finding meaning in work, and social relationships. Workplace well-being and happiness are linked to inner psychological resources like hope and optimism. Factors affecting employees' well-being vary, but overall, it largely affects life satisfaction and physical and mental health at workplace. Various studies have explored the regulation of feeling good and functioning well-being through hedonic and eudaimonic mechanisms. Happiness and relationship are congruent with organizational performance, while health-related well-being appears to function as a conflicting outcome. The UAE oil and gas industry has been influenced by various studies on employee happiness and well-being, with studies showing that it significantly mediates the relationship between job demands and organizational outcomes. Workplace well-being programs improve emotional, physical, and mental well-being after participation. These are relevant for organizations offering and evaluating wellness classes aimed at increasing employee well-being. Employees' narratives of workplace well-being programs' also impact on work productivity and quality of life. Understanding employees' psychological capital, interactional justice, supervisor support, and workplace happiness can help healthcare organizations achieve organizational targets, such as increased job satisfaction.

Exploring previous studies

The researcher reviewed 30 empirical studies on workplace wellbeing and mental health. These studies examined the relationship between teachers' psychological resources, workplace well-being, and perceived workplace happiness. The findings showed that teachers' workplace happiness was influenced by goal realization, feedback, finding meaning in work, and social relationships. Workplace well-being and happiness are linked to inner psychological resources like hope and optimism. Gadhavi et al. (2021) assessed employee happiness at Ganpat University using validated scales. The results indicated that employees at the Indian university are happy, with a positive relationship between life satisfaction, physical and mental health, and employee happiness. However, there is a non-significant relationship between interpersonal relationships and self-affirmation. Factors affecting employees' well-being vary, but overall, the findings suggest that employees at the university are happy, with total life satisfaction and physical and mental health playing a significant role in determining overall happiness. Vivoll Straume & Vittersø (2012) explored the regulation of feeling good and functioning well-being through hedonic and eudaimonic mechanisms. Joo & Lee (2017) examined the impact of perceived organizational support (POS) and psychological capital on

employee happiness in work, careers, and subjective well-being (SWB). Zohreh et al. (2016) examined the relationship between happiness, subjective well-being, creativity, and job performance of primary school teachers in Ramhormoz City. Van De Voorde et al. (2012) explored the role of employee well-being in organizational performance and its relationship with happiness, health, and relationship. The findings suggest that happiness and relationship are congruent with organizational performance, while health-related well-being appears to function as a conflicting outcome. Anderson (2008) investigated the well-being of self-employed individuals using data from the Swedish Level-of-Living Survey. The results showed a positive correlation between self-employment and job satisfaction, but some evidence suggests it leads to more mental health problems and self-employed individuals are less likely to perceive their job as mentally straining. Garg et al. (2009) investigated the impact of psychological wellbeing on organizational commitment of employees. The study found that job satisfaction has a significant direct positive relationship with employee performance and job happiness, while it has a negative insignificant relationship with turnover intention. The UAE oil and gas industry has been influenced by various studies on employee happiness and well-being. Thompson & Bruk-Lee (2021) conducted a study on employee happiness, which found that it significantly mediates the relationship between job demands and organizational outcomes. Jambrino-Maldonado et al. (2022) analyzed international scientific production on the management of happiness and well-being in organizations, revealing notable results. Adnan Bataineh (2019) investigated the relationship between work-life balance, happiness at work, and employee performance in the Med Pharma pharmaceutical industry in Jordan. Pradhan et al. (2017) investigated the impact of employee wellbeing on psychological empowerment, finding a positive association between employee wellbeing and empowerment. Guerci et al. (2022) explored the relationship between employees' perception of high-performance work practices (HPWPs) and health, happiness, and relational well-being. Aghili (2008) investigated the relationship between religious attitude and professional employee happiness, finding that all subscales of religious attitude were highly correlated with happiness. Opatha et al. (2020) studied the impact of HRM on employee happiness in Sri Lanka, finding high levels of happiness and HRM practices. Williams et al. (2017) investigated the role and reprocessing of attitudes in fostering employee work happiness, and Haar et al. (2019) examined the impact of Positive Relational Management (PRM) on employee happiness in New Zealand. Edwards & Marcus (2018) conducted a pilot study in February 2017 to evaluate employee well-being using

the Happiness Mini-Survey and a one-sample pre-post study design. These findings may guide the implementation of policies in the UAE oil and gas industry to enhance employee satisfaction and satisfaction. The study focuses on the impact of workplace well-being programs on employee well-being, with findings showing significant improvements in emotional, physical, and mental well-being after participation. The findings are relevant for organizations offering and evaluating wellness classes aimed at increasing employee well-being. Future studies should use more controlled conditions, a control or comparison group, and qualitative interviews to understand employees' narratives of workplace well-being programs' impact on work productivity and quality of life. Wang et al. (2021) investigated the effects of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) on employees' positive emotions, perceived role overload, and quality of work-life (QWL). Data from 321 hotel employees in China showed that engaging in OCBO generated positive emotions, affecting QWL. However, the study also found a negative relationship between OCBO and perceived role overload, suggesting that OCB can help employees acquire resources and alleviate role overload. Sironi (2019) examined the impact of job satisfaction on optimal well-being variation, independent of individual characteristics. Results showed that job satisfaction had a strong and significantly positive influence on optimal well-being. Boehm & Lyubomirsky (2008) found that happiness is correlated with workplace success, often preceding success measures, and positive affect leads to improved workplace outcomes. Aryan & Kathuria (2017) examined the psychological wellbeing of young employees in private sector IT companies in India, finding a high degree of correlation between psychological wellbeing and well-being. Greenhouse et al. (1987) found that perceptions of a nonsupportive work environment, role conflict, and extensive time commitment were related to well-being. Mendoza-Ocasal et al. (2022) studied the relationship between organizational vision, subjective well-being, work happiness, and quality of life in a group of 302 workers. Babamiri et al. (2023) investigated the relationship between psychological capital, interactional justice, supervisor support, and workplace happiness in Iranian nurses. The study suggests that paying attention to employees' psychological capital, interactional justice, and supervisor support can help healthcare organizations achieve organizational targets, such as increased job satisfaction. Tella et al. (2003) found that macroeconomic movements significantly impact the happiness of nations, with higher unemployment benefits linked to higher national well-being. Meena & Agarwal (2014) explored the relationship between organizational climate, job satisfaction, and happiness,

finding a positive correlation between organizational climate and job satisfaction but also a negative correlation. Uresha (2021) studied the influence of telecommuting on work-life balance and employee happiness in Sri Lankan employees. This study investigates the relationship between telecommuting and work-life balance, employee happiness, and the impact of telecommuting in the Sri Lankan context. A cross-sectional survey of 110 employees revealed a significant positive relationship between telecommuting and these aspects. However, a study by Butt et al. (2020) found that job satisfaction, job inspiration, job security, benefits/salary, work environment, and leadership are the factors determining employee job satisfaction. The study contributes to existing literature on employee job satisfaction and contributes to future research in this area.

Conclusion

Workplace burnout is a common phenomenon around the world and has become a major concern especially after the pandemic. Six main causes of stress leading to burnout include high workloads, unclear job requirements, employee disengagement, low trust, conflict, poorly managed changes, and bullying, harassment, or violence threats. Studies revealed a significant portion of the employees at both public and private sector are suffering from mental health issues which may cost the global economy more than a trillion dollar as predicted by the World Health Organization. Therefore, observing happiness and mental health of employees and secure sustainability is one of the major responsibility for every organization. The present article explored various studies on workplace mental health and wellbeing to echo the crisis that the organizational administrators must take seriously within minimum possible time so that work efficiency and productivity can sustain at a macro level.

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